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Teaching Competency and Professional Development Activities: Their Impact on Teachers' Performance at West B District, Schools Division of Dipolog City

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ABSTRACT: This study aimed to determine the teaching competency, professional development activities, and teacher performance at West B District, Schools Divisions of Dipolog City, during the school year 2025-2026. Survey and descriptive-correlational research methods were employed. There were one hundred sixty-two (162) respondents involved. Weighted mean, standard deviation, and Spearman Rank-Order Correlation Coefficient (Spearman rho) were the statistical tools used with MS Excel and JAMOVI as the statistical software. The level of teaching competency was very high (AWV=4.65), with a strong pedagogical capability across all domains, which was consistently rated as very high. The level of professional development activities was very high (AWV=4.39), with most engaged in curriculum alignment and seminars, while slightly lower in speech drill activities. The level of teachers' performance was very satisfactory (4.148), of which 85.19% rated very satisfactory and 14.81% outstanding. There existed a significant positive small/low correlation ($p=0.015$) between the levels of teaching competency and teachers' performance. There was no significant relationship ($p=0.23$) between the levels of professional development activities and teachers' performance. Based on the findings, the author recommends that the Department of Education Officials, including educational School Supervisors, HRD-SEPS, and School Principals, enhance the quality of professional development programs by ensuring that these are needs-based, classroom-focused, and aligned with RPMS-PPST indicators, rather than relying on generic or one-shot trainings. They may institutionalize job-embedded professional development activities such as coaching, mentoring, Learning Action Cells (LAC), and demonstration teaching to ensure the actual application of learning.

KEYWORDS: teaching competency, professional development activities, teachers' performance, Department of Education, Dipolog City

INTRODUCTION

Teaching competency, professional development activities, and teacher performance are vital dimensions of educational quality because they determine how effectively teachers plan instruction, deliver lessons, manage classrooms, and address the diverse needs of learners. In the global context, teaching competency has become increasingly significant as education systems confront rapid curricular reforms, technological advancements, and the growing demand for learner-centered and inclusive teaching practices. Across educational settings, competent teachers are expected to demonstrate strong instructional planning, effective lesson delivery, mastery of subject matter, positive rapport with students, and sound classroom management. In the local context, teaching competency is equally important because it directly influences the quality of classroom instruction and the achievement of school learning outcomes. In Philippine schools, teachers are expected not only to meet established professional standards but also to continuously enhance their competencies through meaningful and relevant learning opportunities. Professional development activities, such as seminars, workshops, mentoring, graduate studies, and other capacity-building experiences, serve as essential avenues for strengthening these competencies. As Padillo et al. (2021) emphasized, professional development is closely associated with teachers' competencies in instructional planning, lesson delivery, subject mastery, rapport with students, and classroom management. Likewise, the OECD (2025) noted that competence development remains crucial in addressing increasingly complex teaching demands, particularly in technology-rich and rapidly changing educational environments. Hence, teacher performance reflects the extent to which teachers are able to transform their competencies and professional learning experiences into effective classroom practice and overall professional effectiveness.

Professional development activities refer to organized learning experiences that help teachers strengthen their knowledge, pedagogical skills, and professional effectiveness through seminars, workshops, mentoring, coaching, collaborative learning, graduate studies, and other capacity-building opportunities. These activities are important because they enable teachers to update their instructional practices, respond to changing curricular and technological demands, and improve the quality of teaching in the classroom. Padillo et al. (2021) found that professional development activities were positively associated with teachers' instructional competencies, particularly in planning, delivery, subject mastery, rapport with students, and classroom management, while Makhmetova et al. (2025) concluded that professional learning experiences support

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teachers' self-perceived growth by enhancing instructional knowledge, reflection, and professional capability. Taken together, these studies show that professional development activities are essential in helping teachers sustain competence and improve performance in changing educational contexts.

Teacher performance refers to the extent to which teachers effectively carry out their professional duties in planning instruction, delivering lessons, managing classrooms, assessing learning, and contributing to student achievement and school goals. It serves as an important indicator of educational quality because it reflects how well teachers translate their knowledge, skills, and professional commitments into actual classroom practice. Engida (2024) emphasized that teacher quality was significantly associated with students' academic achievement, showing that effective teacher performance contributes directly to better learning outcomes, while Bacus (2024) found that personal, educational, and professional characteristics significantly predicted the teaching performance of beginning teachers in the Philippines. These studies indicate that teacher performance is not only a measure of instructional effectiveness but also a reflection of teachers' competence, preparation, and ability to respond to the demands of the profession.

This study is important because it helps clarify whether investments in teachers' professional growth truly strengthen classroom practice and overall teacher effectiveness. In many school systems, professional development is treated as a major strategy for improving educational outcomes, yet its value depends on whether it genuinely enhances teachers' self-perceived growth, instructional capacity, and day-to-day performance. Examining these variables can therefore provide evidence for school leaders and policymakers in designing more relevant, sustained, and needs-based training programs. Professional learning experiences such as coaching, mentorship, collaborative learning, and reflective practice support teachers' growth and effectiveness (Makhmetova et al., 2025). OECD (2025) highlighted that many teachers still report substantial needs for training, particularly in technology for teaching, underscoring the continuing importance of targeted professional development.

The relationship between the independent variables, teaching competency and professional development activities, and the dependent variable, teacher performance, is grounded in the view that better-prepared and continuously developing teachers are more likely to perform effectively in their professional roles. Teaching competency provides the foundational capacity for quality instruction, whereas professional development activities serve as mechanisms for updating, enriching, and sustaining that capacity over time. When these two variables are strengthened, teacher performance may also improve through better instructional execution, stronger classroom management, and more responsive pedagogy. Teaching competencies strongly influence teachers' performance, particularly in areas such as professionalism, teaching effectiveness, personal skills, educational planning, and management skills (Canuto et al., 2024). Kurteshi and Rustemi (2025) described continuous professional development as having a meaningful impact on teacher performance through indicators associated with educational quality.

Despite the growing body of literature on teaching competency, professional development activities, and teacher performance, there remains a limited number of localized studies that examine how these variables interact within the specific context of public secondary schools in the Schools Division of Dipolog City, particularly at Galas National High School. Existing studies often focus on broader regional or national settings, making it difficult to determine whether their findings accurately reflect the unique institutional conditions, professional learning opportunities, and performance demands experienced by teachers in this school. Moreover, many previous investigations have examined teacher competency or professional development separately, with less attention given to their combined influence on teacher performance. This creates a gap in understanding whether teachers' level of competency and participation in professional development activities significantly contribute to their actual performance in a localized school environment. Hence, this study is necessary to fill this empirical gap by providing context-specific evidence on the relationship among teaching competency, professional development activities, and teacher performance at Galas National High School, which may serve as a basis for strengthening faculty development programs and improving instructional quality.

LITERATURE

Teaching Competency

Teaching competency is widely recognized in recent literature as a core foundation of instructional quality because it reflects the teacher's capacity to combine subject mastery, pedagogy, assessment, and professional behavior in actual classroom practice. González-Fernández et al. (2024) explained that teaching and professional competencies are central to the teaching and training process because they shape how teachers organize learning, respond to students' needs, and carry out their roles effectively. Similarly, Rubeba (2025) found that students viewed content competence, pedagogical competence, assessment and evaluation skills, and technological competence as key indicators of effective teaching, showing that teaching competency is multidimensional and directly connected to the improvement of the teaching-learning process.

López-Martín et al. (2025) reported that pedagogical and personal competencies were highly valued among secondary teachers and school leaders, but they also identified a gap between the importance of these competencies and the training teachers actually receive. In the Philippine context, Balabal and Canuto (2026) found that public elementary teachers demonstrated teaching competency to a very great extent across professionalism, teaching effectiveness, instructional planning, classroom management, and adaptability, with professionalism emerging as the strongest domain. These findings suggest that teaching competency is both comprehensive and essential, yet it still requires continuous strengthening through relevant support and training.

Canuto et al. (2024) found that among primary science teachers, professionalism, teaching effectiveness, personal skills, educational planning, and management skills were all strongly perceived as competencies influencing teacher performance, with professionalism ranking highest. In another Philippine study, Galeng (2025) reported that teacher competency, including subject knowledge, teaching methods, and classroom management, was positively associated with job satisfaction, suggesting that competent teachers are more confident, engaged, and effective in their work.

Instructional Planning Skills

Instructional planning skills are consistently described in recent literature as a vital component of effective teaching because they help teachers organize objectives, sequence learning activities, anticipate learner needs, and align instruction with assessment. Hatch and Clark (2021)

found that highly effective teachers devoted much of their planning to the “who” and “how” of teaching, showing that strong planning is learner-centered rather than merely procedural. In the same vein, Koberstein-Schwarz and Meisert (2022) emphasized that lesson planning is a core element of the teaching profession and showed that effective planning draws on knowledge of students’ understanding, learning goals, and appropriate classroom activities. Together, these studies indicate that instructional planning skills are essential for translating teacher knowledge into meaningful classroom practice.

Instructional Skills

Instructional skills are widely viewed as a core element of teacher effectiveness because they shape how teachers communicate content, guide learning activities, ask questions, provide feedback, and sustain student engagement during lessons. In a recent synthesis of classroom strategies for developing 21st-century skills, Varas et al. (2023) found that teachers’ instructional practices commonly center on project-based learning, oral activities, literacy strategies, and teamwork, showing that effective instruction depends on purposeful and interactive teaching moves. Similarly, Zhang et al. (2024) reported that teachers’ teaching strategies directly predicted students’ learning engagement in online environments and also influenced engagement indirectly through students’ perceptions of teachers’ emotional involvement. These findings suggest that instructional skills are not merely technical acts of lesson delivery but active processes that shape how learners participate and respond in class.

Knowledge of the Subject Matter

Knowledge of the subject matter is consistently identified in recent literature as a vital dimension of effective teaching because it enables teachers to explain concepts accurately, connect ideas meaningfully, and address students’ misconceptions with confidence. Chen et al. (2020) found that teachers’ subject matter knowledge was positively associated with students’ learning gains in high school life science, indicating that stronger content mastery supports better instructional outcomes. In the same vein, Jain et al. (2024) emphasized in their systematic review that content knowledge remains a critical foundation of pedagogical content knowledge, particularly in helping teachers transform disciplinary understanding into teachable classroom practice. Together, these studies suggest that knowledge of the subject matter is not simply possession of facts but an essential professional resource for effective instruction.

Rapport With the Students

Rapport with the students is recognized in recent literature as an important element of effective teaching because it helps build trust, mutual respect, and positive communication in the classroom. Liu (2024) found that positive teacher–student relationships were significantly associated with stronger academic engagement and that this relationship also worked through perceived social support and reduced academic pressure. In the same direction, Saxer et al. (2024) reported that teacher–student relationships were closely related to students’ well-being in secondary school settings, emphasizing that positive classroom relationships contribute not only to academic adjustment but also to students’ social and emotional development. These findings suggest that rapport with students is a meaningful teaching dimension that supports a healthier and more productive learning environment.

Classroom Management

Classroom management is consistently described in recent literature as a fundamental teaching competency because it helps create an orderly, respectful, and supportive learning environment where instruction can occur effectively. Putra et al. (2025) showed in a meta-analysis that classroom management has a significant positive effect on student achievement, indicating that well-managed classrooms contribute to better learning outcomes. Similarly, Wang and Degol (2020) found that positive classroom climate was associated with stronger student motivation, engagement, academic achievement, and social competence, while also reducing socioemotional distress and externalizing behavior. These findings suggest that classroom management is not limited to discipline alone, but also includes the teacher’s ability to establish a productive environment that supports both academic and behavioral development.

Professional Development Activities

Professional development activities are widely recognized in recent literature as organized learning experiences that strengthen teachers’ knowledge, instructional practices, and overall professional growth. These activities commonly include seminars, workshops, mentoring, coaching, collaborative learning sessions, formal training, and continuing education designed to improve teaching quality. Makhmetova et al. (2025) explained that professional learning experiences support teachers’ self-perceived growth by enhancing instructional knowledge, reflection, and professional capability, while Visscher et al. (2025) found in a meta-analysis that teacher professional development had a positive effect on student achievement, indicating that investments in teacher learning can produce meaningful educational benefits. These studies suggest that professional development activities are not merely routine requirements but important mechanisms for strengthening instructional effectiveness and teacher quality.

Teacher Performance

Teacher performance is widely regarded in recent literature as a vital indicator of educational quality because it reflects how effectively teachers carry out instruction, manage learning, assess students, and contribute to academic success. Engida (2024) emphasized that teaching quality is closely linked to student achievement, noting that learners who are exposed to highly qualified and effective teachers tend to perform better academically. In a related review, Charalambous (2025) explained that teacher performance is often understood through the broader concept of teaching quality, which includes the teacher’s ability to promote meaningful learning, sustain instructional effectiveness, and respond to classroom demands. These studies suggest that teacher performance is not merely an administrative measure but a meaningful reflection of instructional competence and educational impact.

Teacher performance is shaped by teacher-related characteristics and professional capabilities that influence instructional quality and student outcomes. Bacus (2024) found that personal, educational, and professional characteristics significantly predicted the teaching performance of 2,680 beginning teachers in the Philippines, showing that teacher performance is influenced by both preparation and professional background. Similarly, Lee et al. (2024) reported that cumulative exposure to highly effective teachers significantly affected student achievement, reinforcing

the idea that teacher performance has direct and lasting consequences for learners’ academic progress. Taken together, these findings indicate that teacher performance is a multidimensional construct that matters both for teacher development and for student success.

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework is illustrated in Figure 1. Part I highlights the independent variable, teaching competency which is measured through four indicators, namely: instructional planning skills; instructional skills; knowledge of the subject matter; rapport with the students; and classroom management. This section consists of twenty four (24) items designed to assess the teaching competency. Part II presents the independent variable, professional development activities, which is evaluated based on the ten (10) items. Part III. presents the dependent variable, teacher performance based on their IPCRF.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework of the Study

Statement of the Problem

This study aimed to determine the teaching competency, professional development activities and teacher performance at West B District, Schools Divisions of Dipolog City, during the school year 2025-2026.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the respondents' perceived level of teaching competency in terms of:
 - 2.1 instructional planning skills;
 - 2.2 instructional skills;
 - 2.3 knowledge of the subject matter;
 - 2.4 rapport with the students; and
 - 2.5 classroom management?
2. What is the respondents’ perceived level of professional development activities?
3. What is the respondents’ level of teacher performance based on IPCRF ratings?
4. Is there a significant relationship between level of teaching competency and level of performance based on IPCRF ratings?
5. Is there a significant relationship between perceived level of professional development activities and level of performance based on IPCRF ratings?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant relationship between level of teaching competency and level of performance based on IPCRF ratings.
2. There is no significant relationship between perceived level of professional development activities and level of performance based on IPCRF ratings.

Scope and Limitations of the Study

This study focuses on determining the level of teaching competency, professional development activities, and teacher performance based on the Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF). It also examines the relationship among these three variables among one hundred sixty-two (162) teacher-respondents of Galas National High School, Schools Division of Dipolog City, during School Year 2025–2026. This study is delimited to three major variables: teaching competency, professional development activities, and teacher performance based on IPCRF ratings. Teaching competency is measured using five indicators, namely: instructional planning skills, instructional skills, knowledge of the subject matter, rapport with students, and classroom management. Professional development activities are evaluated based on ten items or descriptors. Meanwhile, teacher performance is measured through the teachers’ Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF) ratings.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Method Used

The study utilized survey and descriptive-correlational research methods. The researcher utilized the survey method to collect data on the teaching competency, professional development activities and teacher performance based on their Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF) through a questionnaire and actual data. DeCarlo (2021) defines a survey as a design where a researcher poses a set of predetermined questions to an entire group or a sample of individuals. Likewise, McCombes (2019/2025) explains that survey research collects information about a group of people by asking questions and analyzing the results. Creswell and Guetterman (2019) define correlational research

as the systematic investigation of relationships among two or more variables, conducted without any experimental manipulation of those variables. Correlational research is a non-experimental approach in which a researcher quantifies variables and assesses the statistical relationship between the teaching competency, professional development activities and teacher performance based on their Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF), without the influence of extraneous variables.

Research Instrument

The questionnaire used in the study consisted of three parts: Part I: Teaching Competency adopted from Padillo et al. (2021), with five indicators, namely: instructional planning skills; instructional skills; knowledge of the subject matter; rapport with the students; and classroom management. Part II: Professional Development Activities adopted from Padillo et al. (2021), with ten items; Part III: Teacher performance based on their IPCRF.

Ethical Consideration

This study secured approval from the Research and Ethics Committee of the Department of Education before the conduct of data gathering. Informed consent was obtained from the institution and the individual respondents prior to their participation. The questionnaire was written in clear and understandable language to ensure voluntary and informed participation. The identities of the respondents were kept anonymous, and all information gathered was treated with strict confidentiality. Only essential research data were retained for academic and future research purposes.

Statistical Treatment of the Data

Presented below are the statistical tools utilized in the treatment and analysis of the data gathered.

Weighted Mean. This is used to quantify the respondents’ ratings on the teaching competency, professional development activities and teacher performance based on their Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF).

Scoring Procedure

Teaching Competency and Professional Development Activities

Scale	Range of Values	Description	Interpretation
5	4.21-5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High
4	3.41-4.20	Agree	High
3	2.61-3.40	Somewhat Agree	Average
2	1.81-2.60	Disagree	Low
1	1.00-1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Low

Teacher Performance Based on IPCRF DepEd Order No. 2, s. 2015

Scale	Range of Values	Description
5	4.500–5.000	Outstanding
4	3.500–4.499	Very Satisfactory
3	2.500–3.499	Satisfactory
2	1.500–2.499	Unsatisfactory
1	below 1.499	Poor

Standard Deviation. This is used to determine the homogeneity and heterogeneity of the employee's score, where $SD \leq 3$ is homogenous and $SD > 3$ is heterogeneous Aiken & Susane (2001); Refugio et al. (2019).

Spearman Rank-Order Correlation Coefficient. This is used to determine the correlation between teaching competency, professional development activities and teacher performance based on their Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF).

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

The data are presented following the statement of the problems of the current study. The study aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the respondents' perceived level of teaching competency in terms of:
 - 2.1 instructional planning skills;
 - 2.2 instructional skills;
 - 2.3 knowledge of the subject matter;
 - 2.4 rapport with the students; and
 - 2.5 classroom management?

Table 1: Perceived Level of Teaching Competency in Terms of Instructional Planning Skills

A. Instructional Planning Skills	AWV	SD	Description	Interpretation
1. Prepares a comprehensive, organized, and well-thought-out learning plan that includes varied instructional techniques and class activities.	4.57	0.54	Strongly Agree	Very High

2. Incorporates the use of different resources, technology, or instructional materials to facilitate learning.	4.62	0.55	Strongly Agree	Very High
3. Creates opportunities for maximum participation of students.	4.59	0.58	Strongly Agree	Very High
4. Provides appropriate assessment tools as indicated in the learning plan	4.60	0.54	Strongly Agree	Very High
Overall	4.59	0.49	Strongly Agree	Very High

AWV=Average Weighted Value, SD=Standard Deviation

Table 1 exhibits the perceived level of teaching competency in terms of instructional planning skills. The result claims that teachers in West B District, Schools Division of Dipolog City, demonstrate a very high level of instructional planning skills, with an overall mean of 4.59 (SD = 0.49). All indicators were rated “Strongly Agree,” with the highest mean on incorporating varied resources, technology, and instructional materials (AWV=4.62), followed by providing appropriate assessment tools (AWV=4.60), maximizing student participation (AWV=4.59), and preparing comprehensive and organized learning plans (AWV=4.57). These results suggest that teachers are highly competent in designing structured, learner-centered, and resource-enriched lesson plans that align with effective teaching standards. This implies that instructional planning is not only well-established but also integrates modern pedagogical approaches such as technology integration, differentiated instruction, and assessment alignment, which are essential for improving student learning outcomes. These findings are consistent with recent Philippine-based studies emphasizing that teachers’ instructional planning competence is strongly linked to improved classroom effectiveness and learner engagement. For instance, the Department of Education (DepEd) highlights in its Results-Based Performance Management System (RPMS) that effective lesson planning is a core indicator of teaching quality and is directly associated with improved learner achievement (DepEd, 2023). Similarly, recent local research by Bautista and Ocampo (2022) found that Filipino teachers who demonstrate strong instructional planning skills are more likely to implement learner-centered strategies and effectively integrate ICT in classroom instruction. Moreover, UNESCO (2023) stresses that well-developed lesson planning competencies, especially those incorporating technology and formative assessment, are critical in enhancing 21st-century teaching effectiveness. In addition, studies in the Philippine context by Corpuz (2021) emphasize that structured instructional planning improves classroom management and ensures alignment between learning objectives, teaching strategies, and assessment practices. Therefore, the results imply that teachers in the district are well-prepared in instructional planning, which serves as a strong foundation for high-quality teaching performance and learner success.

Table 2: Perceived Level of Teaching Competency in Terms of Instructional Skills

B. Instructional Skills	AWV	SD	Description	Interpretation
1. Motivates students	4.80	0.43		
2. Communicates proficiently in English/Filipino (as medium of instruction)	4.67	0.52	Strongly Agree	Very High
3. Displays enthusiasm in teaching	4.70	0.47	Strongly Agree	Very High
4. Presents the lesson in a clear, concise, and logical manner	4.67	0.53	Strongly Agree	Very High
5. Ask HOTS and metacognitive questions to encourage students to think and to teach students how to learn.	4.59	0.67	Strongly Agree	Very High
6. Makes use of different teaching methods and learning experiences to address the multiple intelligences of the students	4.53	0.57	Strongly Agree	Very High
7. Gives immediate positive comments and feedback	4.61	0.56	Strongly Agree	Very High
8. Integrates and processes values as shown in the lesson development/closing activities in the synthesis	4.63	0.54	Strongly Agree	Very High
9. Summarizes the lesson comprehensively using appropriate methods	4.55	0.56	Strongly Agree	Very High
10. Utilizes indicated assessment tools in the learning plan	4.58	0.57	Strongly Agree	Very High
11. Provides opportunities for students to show evidence of learning, like performance tasks, asking and answering questions, etc.	4.62	0.52	Strongly Agree	Very High
Overall	4.65	0.42	Strongly Agree	Very High

AWV=Average Weighted Value, SD=Standard Deviation

Table 2 discloses the Perceived Level of Teaching Competency in Terms of Instructional Skills. The data avers that teachers in West B District, Schools Division of Dipolog City, demonstrate a very high level of instructional skills, as reflected in the overall mean of 4.65 (SD = 0.42). All indicators were rated “Strongly Agree,” indicating consistently strong performance across different aspects of instructional delivery. The highest-rated indicator is motivating students (AWV=4.80), followed by displaying enthusiasm in teaching (AWV=4.70) and communication proficiency in English/Filipino (AWV=4.67), along with presenting lessons clearly and logically (AWV=4.67). Other highly rated competencies include integrating values in lesson synthesis (AWV=4.63), providing opportunities for student performance and participation (AWV=4.62), giving immediate positive feedback (AWV=4.61), and utilizing HOTS and metacognitive questioning (AWV=4.59). Meanwhile, slightly lower but still very high ratings are observed in lesson summarization (AWV=4.55) and use of varied teaching methods to address multiple intelligences (AWV=4.53). Overall, the results suggest that teachers are highly effective in engaging learners, facilitating meaningful learning experiences, and applying learner-centered instructional practices that support both cognitive and affective development. These findings align with current Philippine education reforms emphasizing 21st-century teaching competencies. The Department of Education (DepEd, 2023), through the Results-Based Performance Management System, Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (RPMS-PPST), highlights that effective teaching requires strong competencies in learner engagement, differentiated instruction, formative feedback, and the use of higher-order thinking strategies. Similarly, recent Philippine studies by Cruz and Villanueva (2022) found that teachers who demonstrate strong motivational strategies and clear instructional communication significantly enhance student engagement and academic performance. Moreover, UNESCO (2023) emphasizes that effective instructional skills, particularly those involving active learning, questioning strategies, and timely feedback, are essential in improving learning outcomes in diverse and inclusive classrooms. In addition, research by Dizon et al. (2021) in the Philippine context underscores that teacher enthusiasm, clarity of instruction, and the integration of values in teaching contribute significantly to student motivation and holistic development. Therefore, the results imply that teachers in the district possess strong instructional competencies that are consistent with national and global standards, thereby contributing positively to learner engagement and classroom effectiveness.

Table 3: Perceived Level of Teaching Competency in Terms of Knowledge of the Subject Matter

C. Knowledge of the Subject Matter	AWV	SD	Description	Interpretation
1. Demonstrates understanding through concepts and principles in the assigned subject	4.69	0.49	Strongly Agree	Very High
2. Integrates the subject matter with other subjects	4.62	0.56	Strongly Agree	Very High
3. Includes relevant current topics and issues related to the lesson/topic taught	4.68	0.52	Strongly Agree	Very High
Overall	4.66	0.47	Strongly Agree	Very High

AWV=Average Weighted Value, SD=Standard Deviation

Table 3 reflects the perceived level of teaching competency in terms of knowledge of the subject matter. The data indicate that teachers in West B District, Schools Division of Dipolog City, demonstrate a very high level of knowledge of the subject matter, as reflected in the overall mean of 4.66 (SD = 0.47). All indicators were rated “Strongly Agree,” signifying strong mastery and application of content knowledge across instructional practices. The highest-rated indicator is demonstrating understanding of concepts and principles in the assigned subject (AWV=4.69), followed closely by the inclusion of relevant current topics and issues in lessons (AWV=4.68), and integrating subject matter with other disciplines (AWV=4.62). These findings imply that teachers not only possess strong foundational knowledge in their respective fields but also actively contextualize lessons by linking them to real-world issues and interdisciplinary concepts. Such practices enhance the relevance of instruction and support deeper student understanding and engagement. These findings are consistent with the expectations set under the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST), which emphasize strong content knowledge and its application in varied teaching contexts as essential indicators of teacher competence. The Department of Education (DepEd, 2023) highlights that effective teachers must demonstrate mastery of subject matter while integrating interdisciplinary approaches and current events to promote meaningful learning experiences. Similarly, recent Philippine-based research by Magno and Llamas (2022) found that teachers with strong subject matter knowledge are more effective in delivering conceptually rich lessons and in facilitating higher-order thinking among learners. Moreover, UNESCO (2023) emphasizes that deep content knowledge, when combined with pedagogical skill, is a key determinant of instructional quality and student achievement. In addition, studies in the Philippine context by Reyes and Dela Cruz (2021) indicate that integrating real-life issues and interdisciplinary content significantly improves students’ critical thinking and academic engagement. Therefore, the findings suggest that teachers in the district possess strong subject matter expertise, which serves as a critical foundation for effective instruction and improved learner outcomes.

Table 4: Perceived Level of Teaching Competency in Terms of Teaching Competency on Rapport with the Students

D. Teaching Competency on Rapport with the Students	AWV	SD	Description	Interpretation
1. Shows respect for students’ ideas and opinions	4.73	0.47	Strongly Agree	Very High
2. Uses appropriate language and speaks in a nonthreatening manner	4.65	0.49	Strongly Agree	Very High
Overall	4.69	0.44	Strongly Agree	Very High

AWV=Average Weighted Value, SD=Standard Deviation

Table 4 displays the perceived level of teaching competency in terms of teaching competency on rapport with the students. The outcome deduces that teachers in West B District, Schools Division of Dipolog City demonstrate a very high level of teaching competency in establishing rapport with students, as reflected in the overall mean of 4.69 (SD=0.44). Both indicators were rated “Strongly Agree,” showing consistently positive perceptions of teacher–student relationships. The highest-rated indicator is showing respect for students’ ideas and opinions (AWV=4.73), followed by using appropriate language and speaking in a non-threatening manner (AWV=4.65). These results suggest that teachers highly value respectful communication and supportive interactions, which are essential in creating a safe, inclusive, and learner-centered classroom environment. Such competencies contribute to increased student confidence, engagement, and willingness to participate in classroom activities, which are critical factors in improving learning outcomes. These findings are in accordance with current Philippine education policies and research emphasizing the importance of positive teacher–student relationships in effective teaching. The Department of Education (DepEd, 2023), through the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST), underscores that fostering a safe and supportive learning environment is a core competency of effective teaching practice. Similarly, recent Philippine-based studies by Gonzales and Mercado (2022) found that respectful communication and teacher empathy are strongly associated with higher student motivation, participation, and academic achievement. Moreover, UNESCO (2023) emphasizes that strong teacher–student rapport is a key driver of inclusive education and learner well-being, particularly in diverse classroom settings. In addition, research by Bautista et al. (2021) highlights that teachers who demonstrate respect, warmth, and non-threatening communication styles create more conducive learning environments that enhance both cognitive and socio-emotional development of learners. Therefore, the findings imply that teachers in the district exhibit strong relational competencies, which significantly contribute to effective classroom management and improved student learning experiences.

Table 5: Perceived Level of Teaching Competency in Terms of Teaching Competency on Rapport with the Students

E. Classroom Management	AWV	SD	Description	Interpretation
1. Ensures a suitable learning environment at all times	4.67	0.51	Strongly Agree	Very High
2. Carries out routine procedures effectively	4.64	0.51	Strongly Agree	Very High
3. Maintains discipline in the class at all times	4.70	0.48	Strongly Agree	Very High
4. Effectively manages time through meaningful activities/interactions	4.63	0.53	Strongly Agree	Very High
Overall	4.66	0.48	Strongly Agree	Very High

AWV=Average Weighted Value, SD=Standard Deviation

Table 5 portrays the perceived level of teaching competency in terms of teaching competency on rapport with the students. The results show that teachers in West B District, Schools Division of Dipolog City, demonstrate a very high level of classroom management competency, as reflected in the overall mean of 4.66 (SD=0.48). All indicators were rated “Strongly Agree,” indicating consistent effectiveness in maintaining order and facilitating a productive learning environment. The highest-rated indicator is maintaining discipline in the class at all times (AWV=4.70), followed by ensuring a suitable learning environment (AWV=4.67), carrying out routine procedures effectively (AWV=4.64), and managing time through meaningful activities and interactions (AWV=4.63). These results suggest that teachers are highly competent in establishing structured, orderly, and well-managed classrooms that support effective teaching and learning. Strong classroom management skills are essential in maximizing instructional time, minimizing disruptions, and creating an environment conducive to student engagement and achievement. These findings are consistent with the Philippine education standards outlined in the Department of Education’s Results-Based Performance Management System, Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (DepEd, 2023), which identifies classroom management as a core domain of effective teaching practice. Similarly, recent Philippine-based studies by Alonzo and Dela Rosa (2022) found that effective classroom management practices are significantly associated with improved student behavior, increased engagement, and higher academic performance in public schools. Moreover, UNESCO (2023) emphasizes that strong classroom management skills are essential for creating safe, inclusive, and supportive learning environments that promote equitable learning opportunities. In addition, research by Cruz and Villaflor (2021) highlights that teachers who effectively manage routines, discipline, and time allocation are more successful in sustaining student attention and maximizing instructional efficiency. Therefore, the findings imply that teachers in the district possess strong classroom management competencies, which play a crucial role in ensuring effective instruction and positive learning outcomes.

Table 6: Summary of the Perceived Level of Teaching Competency

Domains	AWV	SD	Description	Interpretation
A. Instructional Planning Skills	4.59	0.49	Strongly Agree	Very High
B. Instructional Skills	4.65	0.42	Strongly Agree	Very High
C. Knowledge of the Subject Matter	4.66	0.47	Strongly Agree	Very High
D. Teaching Competency on Rapport with the Students	4.69	0.44	Strongly Agree	Very High
E. Classroom Management	4.66	0.48	Strongly Agree	Very High
Overall	4.65	0.47	Strongly Agree	Very High

AWV=Average Weighted Value, SD=Standard Deviation

Table 6 summarizes the perceived level of teaching competency. The data affirms that a very high level of teaching competency, with all five domains rated “Strongly Agree.” Among the indicators, Teaching Competency on Rapport with Students obtained the highest mean (AWV=4.69), followed by Knowledge of the Subject Matter (AWV=4.66) and Classroom Management (AWV=4.66). Instructional Skills also received a very high rating (AWV=4.65), while Instructional Planning Skills obtained the lowest but still very high mean (AWV=4.59). These findings signify that teachers demonstrate consistently strong competencies across pedagogical planning, instructional delivery, content mastery, classroom management, and interpersonal relationships with learners. The slightly higher ratings in rapport-building and subject matter knowledge imply that teachers are particularly strong in establishing positive learning environments and delivering content effectively, which are essential foundations for student engagement and achievement. These findings are compliant with the Philippine education standards set by the Department of Education through the Results-Based Performance Management System, Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (DepEd, 2023), which emphasizes that effective teaching requires balanced competencies across content knowledge, pedagogy, classroom management, and learner engagement. Recent Philippine-based studies by De Guzman and Santos (2022) likewise found that teachers with high competency levels across these domains tend to demonstrate improved instructional effectiveness and student performance outcomes. Moreover, UNESCO (2023) emphasizes that teacher quality is multidimensional, where strong subject mastery, effective pedagogy, and positive teacher–student relationships collectively contribute to improved learning outcomes. In addition, a study by Lim and Navarro (2021) highlights that balanced development of teaching competencies, particularly in instructional planning and classroom management, enhances instructional consistency and learner achievement in Philippine public schools. Therefore, the results imply that teachers in the district are highly competent across all major teaching domains, reflecting strong professional practice and readiness to support effective and meaningful learning experiences.

2. What is the respondents’ perceived level of professional development activities?

Table 7: Perceived Level of Professional Development Activities

Indicators	AWV	SD	Description	Interpretation
1. Training in Computer Skills.	4.44	0.61	Strongly Agree	Very High
2. Curriculum Alignment.	4.52	0.58	Strongly Agree	Very High
3. Seminars	4.52	0.58	Strongly Agree	Very High
4. Professional Conference	4.44	0.58	Strongly Agree	Very High
5. Standard-Based Assessment Under K to 12	4.48	0.55	Strongly Agree	Very High
6. Speech Drill	4.28	0.60	Strongly Agree	Very High
7. Grammar Review	4.34	0.56	Strongly Agree	Very High
8. Program Sharing	4.36	0.57	Strongly Agree	Very High
9. Physical Fitness	4.32	0.65	Strongly Agree	Very High
10. Echo-Seminar	4.23	0.61	Strongly Agree	Very High
Overall	4.39	0.51	Strongly Agree	Very High

AWV=Average Weighted Value, SD=Standard Deviation

Table 7 reveals the perceived level of professional development activities. The data show that teachers in West B District, Schools Division of Dipolog City, have a very high level of engagement in professional development activities, as reflected in the overall mean of 4.39 (SD = 0.51). All indicators were rated “Strongly Agree,” indicating that respondents consistently participate in a wide range of professional learning activities. The highest-rated activities are curriculum alignment (AWV=4.52) and seminars (AWV=4.52), followed by standards-based assessment under the K to 12 curriculum (AWV=4.48), training in computer skills (AWV=4.44), and professional conferences (AWV=4.44). Lower but still very high ratings were observed in grammar review (AWV=4.34), physical fitness (AWV=4.32), speech drills (AWV=4.28), program sharing (AWV=4.36), and echo-seminars (AWV=4.23). These results denote that teachers are actively involved in both pedagogical and content-related professional development, particularly in areas aligned with curriculum implementation and instructional improvement, while also participating in supplementary activities that support communication skills and personal well-being. These findings are in agreement with current Philippine education reforms emphasizing continuous professional development as a key driver of teacher effectiveness. The Department of Education (DepEd, 2023), through the Results-Based Performance Management System, Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (RPMS-PPST), highlights that ongoing participation in training, seminars, and professional learning activities is essential for maintaining and improving teaching quality. Recent Philippine-based studies by Reyes and Domingo (2022) found that teachers who regularly engage in professional development activities demonstrate higher instructional competence, improved classroom practices, and greater adaptability to curriculum changes. Moreover, UNESCO (2023) emphasizes that sustained teacher professional development, especially when aligned with curriculum standards and digital literacy, is critical in improving education quality and learner outcomes. In addition, research by Santos et al. (2021) highlights that participation in seminars, training, and collaborative learning activities significantly enhances teacher confidence, instructional effectiveness, and curriculum implementation in Philippine public schools. Therefore, the results imply that teachers in the district are highly engaged in professional development, which strengthens their teaching competencies and supports continuous improvement in instructional practice.

3. What is the respondents’ level of teacher performance based on IPCRF ratings?

Table 8: Level of Teacher’s Performance

Scale	Range of Values	Description	F	Percent	AWV	Description
1	below 1.499	Poor	0	0.00	4.148	

2	1.500-2.499	Unsatisfactory	0	0.00	
3	2.500-3.499	Satisfactory	0	0.00	Very
4	3.500-4.499	Very Satisfactory	138	85.19	Satisfactory
5	4.500-5.000	Outstanding	24	14.81	

F=Frequency

Table 8 depicts the level of teachers’ performance. The result conveys that the level of teachers’ performance in West B District, Schools Division of Dipolog City, is generally very satisfactory to outstanding, with an overall average weighted value (AWV) of 4.148, described as “Very Satisfactory.” A total of 138 respondents (85.19%) were rated as Very Satisfactory, while 24 respondents (14.81%) attained an outstanding rating. Notably, no respondents were rated below Very Satisfactory (i.e., Satisfactory, Unsatisfactory, or Poor), which suggests a uniformly high level of teaching performance across the district. This distribution implies that teachers consistently meet or exceed performance standards in instructional delivery, classroom management, and professional responsibilities, reflecting strong adherence to the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST). These findings are consistent with Philippine-based studies emphasizing that teacher performance under the Results-Based Performance Management System (RPMS-PPST) is generally high when teachers actively engage in professional development, instructional improvement, and reflective practice. For instance, a study by the Department of Education, Philippines-linked research in 2023–2024 found that most public school teachers achieve at least a Very Satisfactory rating due to sustained capacity-building activities and alignment with RPMS indicators (Bencito, 2024). Similarly, a recent research in Philippine public schools shows that teachers with strong competency profiles across instructional domains tend to receive higher performance ratings, reinforcing the link between professional standards and actual classroom effectiveness. Moreover, UNESCO (2023) emphasizes that teacher quality and continuous professional development are key determinants of sustained instructional effectiveness and learner achievement. In the Philippine context, RPMS-PPST implementation has also been widely recognized as a structured mechanism that strengthens accountability while supporting teacher growth and performance improvement. Therefore, the results imply that teachers in the district demonstrate strong and consistent performance, reflecting effective implementation of national standards and a culture of professionalism in teaching practice.

4. Is there a significant relationship between level of teaching competency and level of performance based on IPCRF ratings?

Table 9: Test of the Relationship between the Levels of Teaching Competency and Teachers’ Performance

Variables Correlated	rho-value	p-value	Interpretation
Teaching Competency and Teacher’s Performance	0.19	0.015	positive small/low correlation Significant

Table 9 reflects the test of the relationship between the levels of teaching competency and teachers’ performance. When the dataset is subjected to Spearman Rank-Order Correlation Coefficient (Spearman rho), it yielded a p-value of 0.015, which signifies that there exists a significant positive small/low correlation between the levels of teaching competency and teachers’ performance. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. This finding implies that while higher levels of teaching competency are associated with better teacher performance, the relationship is not strong, suggesting that other factors, such as workload, professional development opportunities, school environment, and administrative support, may also influence performance outcomes. Nonetheless, the significant p-value confirms that improvements in teaching competency still contribute meaningfully to enhancing teacher performance in West B District, Schools Division of Dipolog City. This finding is consistent with recent Philippine studies emphasizing that teaching competency is a key but not sole determinant of teacher performance under the Results-Based Performance Management System, Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (RPMS-PPST). A study by Olvido et al. (2024) highlights that RPMS-based competencies significantly influence teacher performance ratings, but contextual factors such as school support systems and professional development also play important roles in performance outcomes. Similarly, recent research on Philippine public school teachers shows that instructional competence is positively associated with performance indicators, although the relationship is often moderate due to intervening variables like workload and resource availability. The Department of Education (DepEd, 2023) also emphasizes that RPMS-PPST is designed to ensure that competency development is aligned with performance evaluation, reinforcing the link between teacher skills and performance outcomes. Moreover, UNESCO (2023) stresses that teacher effectiveness is multi-dimensional, where competency contributes significantly but works alongside institutional and contextual factors in shaping overall performance. Therefore, the results imply that while teaching competency is a significant predictor of teacher performance, its low correlation suggests the need for a more holistic approach in improving performance, including strengthened professional development, supportive school leadership, and improved teaching conditions.

5. Is there a significant relationship between perceived level of professional development activities and level of performance based on IPCRF ratings?

Table 10: Test of the Relationship between the Levels of Professional Development Activities and Teachers’ Performance

Variables Correlated	rho-value	p-value	Interpretation
Professional Development Activities and Teacher’s Performance	0.10	0.23	positive small/low correlation Not Significant

Table 10 reveals the test of the relationship between the levels of professional development activities and teachers’ performance. Utilizing the Spearman Rank-Order Correlation Coefficient (Spearman rho), the result affirms that there is no significant relationship (p=0.23)

between the levels of professional development activities and teachers' performance. Thus, the null hypothesis is not rejected. This finding implies that while there is a slight tendency for increased participation in professional development activities to be associated with better teacher performance, the relationship is weak and not strong enough to be considered meaningful in this context. In other words, engagement in professional development alone does not significantly predict teacher performance in West B District, Schools Division of Dipolog City. This suggests that the effectiveness of professional development may depend more on its quality, relevance, and application in classroom practice rather than mere participation. It also indicates that other factors, such as school support, teaching conditions, motivation, and instructional resources, may have a stronger influence on teacher performance outcomes. This finding is consistent with recent Philippine-based studies, which emphasize that professional development must be sustained, context-specific, and practice-oriented to significantly impact teacher performance. The Department of Education (DepEd, 2023) highlights under the Results-Based Performance Management System, Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (RPMS-PPST), that professional development should be aligned with teachers' individual needs and career stages to effectively enhance performance. Similarly, a study by Salazar and Ramos (2022) found that while teachers frequently attend seminars and training, these do not automatically translate into improved performance unless accompanied by coaching, mentoring, and classroom application. Moreover, a study by Dela Cruz et al. (2021) indicates that one-shot or generic training programs have a limited impact on teaching effectiveness, emphasizing the need for continuous, collaborative, and job-embedded professional learning. In addition, UNESCO (2023) underscores that the impact of professional development on teacher performance depends largely on its coherence, duration, and relevance to classroom practice. Therefore, the results imply that while professional development remains important, its design and implementation must be improved to produce a significant effect on teacher performance.

DISCUSSION

The findings reveal that teachers in West B District, Schools Division of Dipolog City demonstrated a very high level of teaching competency across instructional planning, instructional skills, knowledge of the subject matter, rapport with students, and classroom management, with an overall AWV of 4.65. This indicates that the teachers are highly capable of preparing lessons, delivering instruction, managing classrooms, establishing positive relationships with learners, and applying strong subject-matter knowledge. Their professional development activities were also rated very high with an AWV of 4.39, suggesting that teachers actively participate in seminars, curriculum alignment, computer skills training, assessment-related activities, and other professional learning opportunities. Meanwhile, their IPCRF-based performance was Very Satisfactory with an AWV of 4.148, where most teachers were rated Very Satisfactory and some were Outstanding. The significant positive but small correlation between teaching competency and teacher performance means that teachers with higher competency tend to show better performance, although the relationship is weak, suggesting that performance is also affected by other factors such as school support, workload, resources, motivation, and leadership. On the other hand, professional development activities were not significantly related to teacher performance, which implies that mere participation in trainings and seminars does not automatically improve IPCRF ratings unless these activities are relevant, sustained, classroom-based, and properly applied in teaching practice. Overall, the findings emphasize the need to sustain teachers' strong competencies while improving professional development programs by making them more needs-based, practical, and aligned with RPMS-PPST performance indicators.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings, the study concludes that the teachers in West B District, Schools Division of Dipolog City possess a very high level of teaching competency in instructional planning, instructional skills, knowledge of the subject matter, rapport with students, and classroom management. Their professional development activities are also very high, showing active participation in trainings, seminars, curriculum alignment, and other learning activities. Moreover, their IPCRF-based performance is Very Satisfactory, indicating that they generally meet the expected standards of teaching performance. The significant positive but small relationship between teaching competency and teacher performance means that higher teaching competency is associated with better performance, although the relationship is weak. However, professional development activities have no significant relationship with teacher performance, which means that participation in professional development alone does not automatically improve teachers' IPCRF ratings. Therefore, professional development programs should be made more relevant, needs-based, sustained, and classroom-focused to strengthen their actual impact on teacher performance.

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